

The Effect of Promotions on Customer Satisfaction on the Tokopedia Partner Application

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ABSTRACT

Business developments in the field of buying and selling have developed, especially in Indonesia, requiring Tokopedia Partners to carry out appropriate marketing strategies to be more competitive by providing satisfaction to customers who purchase products/services at Tokopedia Partners so that they can maintain existing ones as well as to attract potential customers. new and can achieve the target according to the expectations of the company. The aim of this study is to analyse the effect of advertising, personal selling, sales promotion, and public relations on consumer satisfaction when purchasing products or services. Companies use promotion as a set of tools to communicate their products to consumers and make a profit. Customers can feel either pleased or disappointed with the experience they have had with a company's products. The company's aim should be to fulfil their wants and needs. This research was carried out using a survey method, with data collection techniques based on questionnaires, documentation and library studies on objects of interest. The number of respondents who were sampled were 56 respondents who had used the Tokopedia Mitra application consisting of 11 people whose shop type was permanent, The study collected data from 13 individuals with semi-permanent shops, 23 individuals with wholesale shops, and 10 individuals with individual shops. Descriptive analysis was used to analyze the data. The results indicate that the promotion mix has a strong positive effect on customer satisfaction, with a relationship between variables of 0.759 or 75.9%, and an effect of 57.6%

INTRODUCTION

Research Background

Technological developments are currently developing very rapidly, one example is buying and selling activities that are carried out online. Until now, industrial development has been marked by changes in each era, namely Revolution 1.0, 2.0, and 3.0, and until now it has reached Industrial Revolution 4.0. In each phase, the economic sector moves differently.

With the emergence of Industrial Revolution 4.0, world technological developments are changing increasingly rapidly. This industrial revolution certainly has a positive impact on technological development, but some problems hinder this development. In Indonesia itself, several obstacles were found that made the Indonesian Industrial Revolution 4.0 difficult to implement. Barriers in E-Commerce. The first is trust. Trust here is a very prominent obstacle in electronic commerce because, in our own country, we are more confident in using face-to-face transactions or direct purchases, where we can see, touch or even try it on and ensure that the size is truly real when making transactions. sale. This is different from Western people such as those in England who are used to transacting online or ordering using catalogs, then just sending and waiting for the goods they have ordered.

In the Industrial Revolution 4.0 era, competition between industries is very tight. In today's business world, the level of competition between business industries is increasingly sharp, including companies in Indonesia. Increasingly fierce competition in the business world has spread to all business sectors so the competition between companies is getting tighter. Promotion is a very important function in a company, where with proper marketing it can determine sales volume and company position.

Because decisions taken in the field of marketing should be aimed at determining products, markets, prices, and promotions. The entire system of business activities must be market or consumer-oriented. Tokopedia Partners every day provides promotions that attract the interest of their customers. Tokopedia Partners also ensure that their customers feel that their needs are met so that Tokopedia Partners can obtain business continuity which is very important for the company, so that customers have a good view and are satisfied with Tokopedia Partners.

Based on the description above, the authors want to find out more about how much influence promotion has on customer satisfaction, whether promotion has an effect on customer satisfaction or has no effect on customer satisfaction. Thus, the authors are interested in conducting research entitled "The Influence of Promotions on Customer Satisfaction in the Tokopedia Partner Application".

Formulation of the problem

Based on the research problem limitations above, the formulation of this research problem is as follows:

1. How is the promotion on the Tokopedia Partner application in Depok City
2. How is customer satisfaction with the Tokopedia partner application in Depok City
3. What is the influence of the promotional mix on customer satisfaction on the Tokopedia partner application in Depok City

Theoretical Basis and Framework of Thinking Management

The word management comes from the Latin words manus which means hand and agree which means to do. The words are combined into the verb manager which means to handle. Manager in English in the form of the verb to manage, with the noun management, and manager for people who carry out management activities. Then management is translated into Indonesian into management or management.

According to Richard L. Daft (2012: 8), management is the achievement of organizational goals effectively and efficiently through planning, organizing, leading, and controlling organizational resources.

According to Lawrence A. Appley (2010: 16), defining management is a skill that a person or organization has to move other people to do something.

From the definition presented, it can be concluded that management is a process carried out to achieve organizational goals by working in a team.

Management Function

According to Amirullah (2015; 8), management functions are generally divided into four functions, namely planning, organizing, directing and, supervising functions to achieve the desired results effectively and efficiently.

a) Planning :

Planning is the process of forming and determining targets and goals to be achieved by mutual agreement through strategic steps to achieve the existing vision and mission. Through planning, a manager gets the desired picture to carry out the process.

b) Organizing:

Organizing is the process of coordinating each resource in the form of individuals or groups to implement plans that have been made, coordinating each individual or group towards agreed activities.

c) Direction:

Direction is a process to provide motivation and direction to employees so that they still have the spirit of work and can also carry out these activities efficiently and effectively for the company.

d) Control:

Control is the supervision of activities to maintain the conformity of activities with the agreed vision and mission, and also maintain the quality or standards of employee performance to take corrective action if necessary.

Marketing Management

Philip Kotler and Kevin Lane Keller in marketing management book, Marketing is Identifying and Meeting Human and Social Needs. One good and concise definition of marketing is "meeting needs profitably."

According to Sumerian (2015: 17), marketing is the process of identifying consumer needs and then producing goods or services so that transactions or exchanges take place between producers and consumers.

According to Sunyoto (2012:217), marketing is a management process that aims to achieve the desired response through a carefully formulated programme. Based on the definitions provided by experts, it can be concluded that marketing is a crucial activity for companies to ensure their survival, whether they offer goods or services. Marketing involves direct interaction with consumers and can be defined as human activities that take place in the market. Therefore, businesses must focus their activities towards the market or consumers.

Marketing Mix

The Marketing Mix is a set of marketing variables used to reach the right target market. It consists of either 4P or 7P, depending on the marketing strategy employed.

According to Kotler and Armstrong, quoted from the book *Marketing Management: In 'A Strategy for Increasing Customer Loyalty'* (Lili Suryati, 2015:17), the marketing mix is defined as a set of tools that companies use to achieve their goals in the target market.

Tjiptono (2018) explains that Jerome McCarthy popularized the marketing mix several decades ago, formulating it into 4Ps: product, price, place, and promotion.

Tjiptono (2014:41) defines the marketing mix as a set of tools used by marketers to shape the characteristics of the services offered to customers.

1) Product

Products are goods or services that are designed in such a way to be marketed.

2) Price

Once the products and services we want to market exist, then we determine the selling price of the product/service.

3) Place

Place is a distribution channel used to reach target consumers. It includes location, transportation, warehousing, and more.

4) Promotion

Promotion refers to activities that communicate the advantages of a product and encourage customers to purchase it. Promotions are intended to make demand more responsive to changes in price, becoming more elastic when prices fall and less elastic when prices rise.

5) People

The next element is people or human resources. When a company or organization experiences growth in terms of credibility and broad business coverage, the next step is to determine the company's internal organizational structure. Where you will need several people in positions that suit the abilities and expertise of each human resource. When taking on recruits or employees, many things must be considered. First, from the intellectual side, recruitment must meet the applicable terms and conditions. Then, have a good attitude or attitude so that every work process can be carried out optimally and consistently. The most important thing is, to have good experience and integrity. Employees who have a lot of experience can have a good influence on the company.

6). Physical Evidence

This marketing mix element is also very important to implement. Attractive packaging can increase product sales factors. In general, customers will pay attention to the structure and appearance of the packaging that has been made. Next, customers will see the contents of the product.

7). Process

The last component of the 7P marketing mix is the process. In this context, process refers to the procedures, mechanisms, and flows that consumers use to access existing services. Therefore, this element encompasses the consumer experience from the initial introduction of the product to the purchasing process.

Promotion

In general, promotion is a part of a series of marketing activities for a product or field. It involves communication from a company to buyers or consumers, including information, persuasion, and influence, all aimed at increasing sales.

According to Tjiptono (2010:219), Vania et al (2019), Promotion is a marketing activity that aims to spread information, influence, persuade, or expand the target market for a company and its products. The goal is to encourage customers to accept and remain loyal to the products offered by the company.

Promotion Indicator

Promotion indicators are presented as promotion elements.:

- 1) Advertising
- 2) Personal selling
- 3) Sales promotion
- 4) Direct Sales
- 5) Public Relations

Satisfaction

Kotler and Armstrong (2012:36) define satisfaction as the comparison of customer value between the benefits and costs incurred to accept the offer. Lovelock and Wirtz (2011:74) state that satisfaction is an attitude based on experience. It is an assessment of the product or service's characteristics and features, providing consumer pleasure in fulfilling consumption needs. Consumer satisfaction can be achieved through quality, service, and value. Providing high customer value is the key to generating customer loyalty.

Customer

According to Nasution (Rusydi, 2017:3) It has been stated that customers are individuals who demand that the company meets certain quality standards, and therefore they can have an impact on the company's performance. According to (Rusydi, 2017:3) states that "a customer is someone who comes or has the habit of buying something from a seller. This ability includes the activity of purchasing and paying for several products repeatedly." From the definitions above, it can be concluded that a customer is anyone who buys products or services that are sold regularly

Customer satisfaction

According to Kasmir (Islami, 2018) "customer Satisfaction refers to the level of contentment a consumer experiences after comparing their expectations with what they received. If a customer is satisfied with the value provided by a product or service, they are more likely to remain a customer in the long term. According to Irawan (Dewa, 2018), customer satisfaction contributes to several crucial aspects, such as the creation of customer loyalty, improvement of the company's reputation, reduction of price elasticity, reduction of future transaction costs, and improvement of employee efficiency and productivity".

Customer Satisfaction Indicators

Because there are so many customers using the product each customer uses it differently, behaves differently, and speaks differently. Indicators of customer satisfaction according to Hawkins and Lonney quoted in Tjiptono (2015:101) are as follows

- 1) Conformity of expectations refers to the level of agreement between the expected and perceived product performance by customers.
- 2) Interest in revisiting pertains to the customer's willingness to return or purchase related products.
- 3) Willingness to recommend measures a customer's likelihood to recommend products they have experienced to friends or family.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Customer Satisfaction Indicators

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Conceptual Framework

Based on the above phenomena and the theoretical basis, a relevant research framework can be used to obtain the right research process so that answers to the questions in the problem formulation are obtained, namely, how does the Promotion Mix influence Customer Satisfaction in the Tokopedia Partner application in Depok City

The Research Framework is as Follows:

Figure 1. Framework
 Source : Olahan Pribadi

Hypotesis

Based on the problem formulation provided, the following hypothesis is formulated: 'There is a suspected influence between promotion and customer satisfaction', with the following criteria: H0: There is no positive relationship between promotion (x) and consumer satisfaction (y), and Ha: There is a positive relationship between promotion (x) and consumer satisfaction (y).'

METHODOLOGY

Place and Time of Research

To obtain the necessary data for this thesis, the author conducted research in Mekarjaya Village, Depok 2 Tengah, West Java from November 2021 to February 2022.

Population and Sample

It is important to note that population is not just the number of objects or subjects being studied, but also includes all the characteristics or traits possessed by the subject or object. The population in the current research conducted by the author consists of customers who have used or are still using the Mitra Tokopedia application, totaling 100 people. The total research sample was 56 Mitra Tokopedia customers, as calculated above.

Research Variable

According to Sugiyono (2018:39), a research variable is an attribute, trait, or value of a person, object, or activity that has certain variations determined by the researcher to be studied and conclusions drawn. This research includes two variables: the independent variable (X) represented by promotion and the dependent variable (Y) represented by customer satisfaction.

Data Collection Technique

Data collection techniques are employed to gather data in accordance with research procedures to ensure the necessary information is obtained.

1. Literature Study

Library study is the activity of collecting data and information by taking books and other sources from the library.

2. Studi Lapangan

Field studies by conducting studies directly on the target object. The intended objects in this case are customers who have or are still using the Tokopedia partner application in the Mekarjaya sub-district, Depok 2 Tengah City, West Java

3. Kuesioner

Sugiyono (2018:193) The text explains that a questionnaire is a technique for collecting data by providing a set of questions or written statements to the residents who have rented the property.

4. Documentation

Sugiyono (2018:240) The text explains that documents are records of past events in the form of writing, drawings, or monumental works. In this research, documentation takes the form of the location of the research site.

Data Analysis Technique

- Validity Test

Syofian (2013:46) explains that validity or validity testing is showing the extent to which a measuring instrument can measure what it wants to measure. The testing technique for testing the validity of this research data uses Pearson Correlation.

- Reliability Test

Sugiyono (2018:130) explains that research instruments whose reliability is tested using a retest test are carried out by trying the instrument several times on respondents, in this case, the instrument is the same, the respondents are the same and the times are different.

- Descriptive Statistical Analysis and Discussion

Simple Regression Analysis J.Supranto (2016:179) explains that it is impossible to estimate the relationship between two variables without first making assumptions regarding the form of the relationship expressed in a particular function. In some cases, we can check these assumptions after the relationships have been estimated. Linear functions have the following equation form

Where:

Y = Consumer Satisfaction

X = Promotion Mix

a, b = Constant

Correlation Analysis Test

This technique is also known as the Pearson correlation coefficient. Pearson Product Moment Correlation is a popular correlation analysis technique. It was proposed by Karl Pearson in 1900.

Coefficient of Determination

According to Syofian (2014:252), the coefficient of determination is a numerical value that indicates the contribution of one or more independent variables (X) to the dependent variable (Y). The formula for calculating the coefficient of determination is provided below:

$$Kd = r^2 \times 100\% \text{ Where:}$$

$$Kd = \text{Coefficient of determination}$$

$$r^2 = \text{Correlation value obtained}$$

If the obtained value of (r^2) is close to 1, it can be concluded that the model strongly explains the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. Conversely, if (r^2) is closer to 0, the influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable is weaker.

Hypothesis test

Uji Signifikansi Uji-T

The T-test is a partial test used to evaluate the influence of each independent variable on the dependent variable individually. This test can be performed by comparing the t count with the t table or by examining the significance column in each t count. The t-test employs the same output table as the regression table.

Under the condition :

- 1). If t count > t table then there is a strong influence between the independent variable (product diversity) and the dependent variable (consumer loyalty).
- 2). If t count < t table then there is a weak influence between the independent variable (product diversity) and the dependent variable (consumer loyalty).

This t-test is used to prove the truth of the research hypothesis that there is a significant influence between variable X (product diversity) on variable Y (consumer loyalty).

The statistical hypothesis formula is:

$$H_a \text{ (alternative) is accepted if } = t \text{ count} > t \text{ table}$$

$$H_o \text{ (zero) is accepted if } = t \text{ count} < t \text{ table}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

PT. Tokopedia is an Indonesian online mall that operates on a marketplace and online mall business model. It provides a platform for sellers and buyers to conduct safe and convenient online transactions. Joining Tokopedia is free and easy. Since its inception, www.tokopedia.com has experienced rapid growth and has become one of Indonesia's leading online marketplaces. Despite being in its early stages, the platform has a significant number of members, stores, and active online users. Additionally, there are a large number of products available for purchase, and numerous buying and selling transactions occur daily. Tokopedia

has been able to compete in the Indonesian marketplace market, apart from having different methods from its competitors, Tokopedia is able to continue to advance in e-commerce business competition. Tokopedia does not have any subsidiary companies. It solely operates from its head office located in Jakarta, but has a wide user base of sellers throughout Indonesia.

In 2018 the Tokopedia partner application was launched. Since being introduced in November 2018, the Mitra Tokopedia application has now been downloaded by almost two million Android users. This lightweight application measuring 3 MB continues to make it easier for Indonesian people to develop their businesses, especially stall owners, grocery stores and other similar businesses. The Tokopedia Partner application also helps bridge the Indonesian people to enjoy an online-to-offline (O2O) shopping experience.\

The Tokopedia Partner application makes it easier for shop owners, grocery stores and other similar businesses to sell various kinds of digital products, such as credit, water bills, game vouchers and so on, as well as buy stock of goods via the Wholesale feature. With this convenience, stall owners, grocery stores and other similar businesses can get better profits. More alternative products are being sold

Vision

Tokopedia has a vision to build a better Indonesia via the internet

Mission

Tokopedia's mission is to achieve digital economic equality

Instrument Test Description

Validity Testing

The validity test is used to measure whether a questionnaire is valid or not. Validity testing in this research was carried out using Pearson Correlation. This question item is said to be valid if the results of R Count > R Table. In testing the validity of R Table = 0.266. This test uses 10 questionnaires, for information can be seen in the following table:

Table 1. Calculation of the Validity of the Independent Variable (X)

NO	PROMOTIONAL INDICATOR QUESTIONNAIRE (X)									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
R table	0,266	0,266	0,266	0,266	0,266	0,266	0,266	0,266	0,266	0,266
R Count	0,701409	0,724221	0,6052	0,64757	0,66556	0,6137	0,63737	0,748606	0,62142	0,5971898
INFORMATION	valid	valid	valid	Valid	valid	valid	valid	valid	valid	valid

Sumber : Olan Pribadi

Table 2. Calculation of the Validity of the Dependent Variable (Y)

NO	CUSTOMER SATISFACTION INDICATOR QUESTIONNAIRE (Y)									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
R Table	0,266	0,266	0,266	0,266	0,266	0,266	0,266	0,266	0,266	0,266
R Count	0,696812	0,641717	0,729503	0,524734	0,616596	0,578805	0,727437	0,698464	0,673305	0,646781
INFORMATION	Valid	Valid	Valid	Valid	Valid	Valid	Valid	Valid	Valid	Valid

Source: Olan Pribadi

Based on the data presented above, all instruments have a calculated R-value greater than the R table value (0.266). Therefore, it can be concluded that the research instruments used are valid.

Reliability Testing

The study's reliability test employed the Cronbach's alpha formula. An instrument is considered reliable if the Cronbach Alpha coefficient value exceeds 0.6. The reliability test results are presented in the table below.

Table 3. Testing the Reliability of Independent and Dependent Variables

VARIABLE	<i>Cornbach's Alpha</i>	<i>N of Items</i>	INFORMATION
Promotion (X)	0,848487843	10	Realible
Customer satisfaction (Y)	0,846850326	10	Realible

Source : Olahan Pribadi

From the table above, it can be concluded that the reliability value of the independent variable is 0.848 and that of the dependent variable is 0.846. This indicates that the reliability coefficient value is greater than 0.6, which suggests that the research instrument used is reliable.

Data Analysis and Discussion

Promotions on Tokopedia

The promotions produced by Tokopedia Partners after giving several statements to Tokopedia Partner Customers are as follows:

Table 4. Percentage of Tokopedia Partner Customers Who Strongly Agree and Agree With Variable

INDICATOR	NUMBER OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
Advertising	43	76,2
Personal sales	47	83,9
Sales promotion	46	83
Public relations	49	87,3

Source: Olahan Pribadi

Based on the table data above, customers who stated Agree and Strongly Agree with statements from actors or advertising obtained a percentage of 76.2%, Personal Sales of 83.9%, Sales Promotion of 83% and Public Relations of 87.3%. Results This states that Advertising is still lacking and Public Relations is an important factor for Tokopedia Partners

Table 5. Percentage of Tokopedia Partner Customers Based on Total Score Regarding Variable X

Indicator	Total Answer Value	Percentage (%)
Advertising	651	29
Personal Sales	684	30
Sales promotion	455	20
Public relations	466	21
Total score	2256	100

Source: Olahan Pribadi

Based on the total score table data above, it states that advertising gets a score of 29%, personal sales gets a score of 30%, sales promotions get a score of 20%, and public relations get a score of 21%.

Customer Satisfaction on the Tokopedia Partner Application

The customer satisfaction given by Tokopedia Partners after being given several statements to Tokopedia Partners customers is as follows:

Table 6. Percentage of Tokopedia Partner Customers Who Agree and Strongly Agree with Variable Y

Indicator	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Conformity to Expectations	49	87,9
Interested in Returning	52	93,4
Willingness to Recommend	51	90,4

Source : Olahan Pribadi

Based on the total score table above, it states that the Conformity of Expectations indicator gets a score of 40%, and the Intent to Revisit and Willingness to Recommend indicators get a score of 30% each.

The Effect of Promotions on Customer Satisfaction in the Tokopedia Partner Application

Simple Linear Regression Analysis

This research employs multiple linear regression to determine the influence of the Promotion (X) and Customer Satisfaction (Y) variables, using the following equation:

$$Y = a + bX$$

Information

Y = Customer Satisfaction

X = Promotion

a,b = Constant

Simple linear regression calculations can be performed using SPSS 25 for Windows based on the obtained data. The results of the multiple linear regression test using SPSS 25 for Windows are presented below.

Table 7. Coefficientsa

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	15.140	3.153		4.802	.000
	PROMOTION	.665	.078	.759	8.564	.000

a. Dependent Variable: CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

Sourcer : Olahan SPSS

From the results of the calculations above, a simple regression equation can be obtained as follows:

$$Y = a + bX$$

$$Y = 15,140 - 0,665X$$

The above regression equation can have the following explanation.

The constant of 15,140; means that if the Promotion Factor (X) value is 0, then the customer satisfaction (Y') value is 15,140

If the promotion variable (X) increases by 1 unit, customer satisfaction will increase by 0.665. If the promotion variable decreases by one unit, the customer satisfaction variable decreases by 0.665.

Correlation Analysis Test

Correlation between Y by controlling the influence of X

The correlation between Promotions and Customer Satisfaction of the Tokopedia Partner application using SPSS 25 is as follows

Table 8. Correlations

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.759 ^a	.576	.568	2.952

a. Predictors: (Constant), PROMOSI

Source: Olahan Spss

From the analysis above, the correlation/relationship value obtained is R of 0.759 or 75.9%, meaning that the two variables are strong or positive and both are in the same direction, in other words, this correlation value is classified as very strong positive. The level of customer satisfaction increases with higher levels of promotion.

Coefficient of Determination

The coefficient of determination has been calculated, and the results are as follows:

$$Kd = r^2 \times 100\%$$

$$Kd = 0,576 \times 100\%$$

$$Kd = 57,6\%$$

The coefficient of determination is the percentage influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable, as explained. R² of 0.576. 57.6% of the dependent variable is influenced by the independent variable, while the remaining percentage is influenced by other variables.

Hypothesis testing

T-test

Tabel 8. Coefficientsa

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	15.140	3.153		4.802	.000
	PROMOTION	.665	.078	.759	8.564	.000

a. Dependent Variable: CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

Source: Olahan SPSS

The regression equation is $y = 15.140 - 0.665x$.

This indicates that T count 8.564 is greater than T table 0.266, proving the hypothesis and rejecting H0 while accepting Ha if the test is carried out partially. The formulated hypothesis is: 'There is a suspected influence between promotion and customer satisfaction' with the following criteria:

H0: There is no positive relationship between the promotional mix (x) and consumer satisfaction (y).

Ha: There is a positive relationship between the promotional mix (x) and consumer satisfaction (y).

CONCLUSIONS

From the results of the data analysis that has been carried out and the discussion that was presented in the previous chapter, several research conclusions can be drawn with the following explanation:

1. Based on the results of respondents' responses distributed via questionnaire, it can be concluded that the statement from the Public Relations indicator obtained the highest percentage, namely 87.3% with a total score of 466, and was chosen by an average of 49 respondents. Meanwhile, the statement of the Advertising indicators implemented by Tokopedia Partners obtained the lowest percentage of 76.2%, with a total score of 651. This means that according to consumers, the Public Relations carried out are considered important by Tokopedia Partners

2. Based on the results of respondents' responses distributed through questionnaires, it can be concluded that the statement of the Conformity of Expectations indicator obtained a percentage of 87%, Interest in Returning to Visit received a percentage of 93.4%, and Willingness to Recommend obtained a percentage of 90.4%. This states that Tokopedia Partner Customer Satisfaction is quite high, with a very high percentage of Interest in Returning, however, the Conformity of Expectations needs to be considered again because it has the lowest percentage among the three other indicators.

3. Based on simultaneous testing, the analysis indicates a strong positive correlation (75.9%) between the independent variable (Promotion) and the dependent variable (Consumer Satisfaction), with Promotion accounting for 57.6% of the total effect. The analysis indicates a strong positive correlation (75.9%) between the independent variable (Promotion) and the dependent variable (Consumer Satisfaction), with Promotion accounting for 57.6% of the total effect. Other variables also have an influence on the results. If the result of the T-test is 0.00, which is smaller than 0.05 (α) or if the T count is 8.564 and greater than the T table of 0.266, then the hypothesis is proven. In this case, H0 is rejected and Ha is accepted, if the test is carried out partially.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Suggestions that researchers can give to Tokopedia Partners based on the results of the research that has been carried out are as follows:

1. Future researchers are expected to conduct research outside the existing variables of the promotion mix such as product, price and place factors because the R^2 value in this research is still too small.
2. Tokopedia partners are advised to pay more attention to their advertising activities to attract new customers and also retain existing customers because based on the answers advertising activities have the lowest percentage compared to other indicators.
3. Tokopedia partners must pay attention to the suitability of customer expectations because they get the lowest presentation compared to other indicators

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations, so it is necessary to carry out further research related to the topic of The Effect of Promotions on Customer Satisfaction in order to improve this research and add insight to readers.

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